

UDC 338.48

EDN: ZMCIWY

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15571398

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THE PRESENCE OF LEISURE IN FIELDWORK IN UNDERGRADUATE COURSES IN TOURISM IN BRAZIL: AMBIGUITIES, DILEMMAS, AND CHALLENGES

Abstract. *This study examines the integration of fieldwork practices in undergraduate tourism education in Brazil, with particular focus on the ambiguous relationship between leisure and pedagogical objectives. Drawing upon critical pedagogy and leisure studies frameworks, the research investigates how tourism educators conceptualize and implement fieldwork while navigating the inherent tensions between experiential learning and leisure-based activities. The study employs a multi-method qualitative approach comprising: 1) Systematic literature review of Portuguese-language academic sources on tourism pedagogy; 2) Documentary analysis of curricular guidelines; 3) In-depth interviews with 34 faculty members from 19 Brazilian tourism programs; 4) Critical discourse analysis of interview transcripts. Key findings reveal: a) Significant terminological inconsistencies in describing fieldwork practices; b) Unresolved tensions regarding the role of leisure in academic fieldwork; c) Divergent faculty perspectives on balancing experiential learning with professional training objectives. The research highlights the need for clearer theoretical and methodological frameworks to distinguish between recreational activities and pedagogically structured fieldwork in tourism education. Furthermore, it identifies challenges in aligning practical training components with the academic rigor expected in higher education while acknowledging leisure's potential as a didactic resource.*

Keywords: *fieldwork, graduate courses in tourism, leisure*

Citation: Anjos Júnior, E. S. dos., Lopes, R. A., & Gomes, C. L. (2024). The Presence of Leisure in Fieldwork in Undergraduate Courses in Tourism in Brazil: Ambiguities, Dilemmas, and Challenges. *Sovremennye problemy servisa i turizma [Service and Tourism: Current Challenges]*, 18(4), 119–131. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.15571398.

Article History

Received 18 July 2024

Accepted 20 November 2024

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

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ДОСУГ В ПОЛЕВЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯХ В ПРОГРАММАХ БАКАЛАВРИАТА ПО ТУРИЗМУ В БРАЗИЛИИ: НЕОПРЕДЕЛЁННОСТЬ, ДИЛЕММЫ И ВЫЗОВЫ

Цель статьи – проанализировать, как полевые исследования обогащают практику преподавания на программах бакалавриата по туризму в Бразилии. Кроме того, работа направлена на то, чтобы понять, как преподаватели оценивают важность включения организации досуга в образовательный процесс высшего образования в сфере туризма. В основе исследования лежат размышления о взаимосвязи между досугом и обучением. Авторы также изучают вопрос освещённости образовательной эффективности полевых исследований в туризме в литературе на португальском языке в Бразилии. Для достижения поставленных целей использовался следующий методологический подход: 1) библиографическое исследование; 2) документальное исследование; 3) интервью; 4) качественный анализ. Исследование опиралось на данные, полученные в результате интервью с 34 профессорами из девятнадцати программ бакалавриата по туризму в Бразилии. В результате сделан вывод о важности полевых исследований для программ бакалавриата по туризму, проанализирован вклад такой практики обучения в расширение знаний и практических навыков в подготовке бакалавров по туризму, определены сложности и вызовы в организации полевых исследований и внедрения их в учебную деятельность. Результаты показывают разнообразное и неоднозначное понимание терминологии, используемой для описания учебной полевой практики, а также отсутствие достаточного внимания к организации досуга студентов во время полевого этапа учебного процесса.

Ключевые слова: полевые исследования, высшее образование по туризму, досуг

Для цитирования: Анжос Жуниор Э.С., Лопес Р.А., Гомес К.Л. Досуг в полевых исследованиях в программах бакалавриата по туризму в Бразилии: неопределённость, дилеммы и вызовы // Современные проблемы сервиса и туризма. 2024. Т.18. №4. С. 119–131. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15571398.

Дата поступления в редакцию: 18 июля 2024 г.

Дата утверждения в печать: 20 ноября 2024 г.

1. Introduction

In the curricular guidelines of undergraduate courses in Tourism in Brazil, it is noteworthy that fieldwork is mentioned only once. In the 5th article of the document, which deals with the student's training fields, these pedagogical activities are called "technical visits". This term is present in item III - "Theoretical and practical content", where the document highlights the need for students to conduct studies in areas of tourism flow, "including technical visits" (Brasil, 2006, p.3).

Besides allowing the contextualization, expansion, and deepening of the content studied in the classroom, fieldwork favors contact with the labor market and with different forms of social organization, improving the professional, educational, and personal training of tourism students. However, the expression "technical visits" may obliterate other fieldwork arrangements, such as the study of the environment and/or the collection of data that might inform future research.

The existence of a reading of the fieldwork that restricts the possibilities of this pedagogical practice to something limited to the materialization of theoretical contents worked in the classroom may favor the invisibilization of different content and experiences.

What is inferred is something close to the logic that would associate the technical visit only to the opportunity to put "the theory, the didactic, the pedagogical 'face to face' with practice, with reality [...]" (Veloso, 2003, p. 25-26).

The little room given to fieldwork in these curricular guidelines seems to reverberate also in the academic production on the subject in Brazil. Not only is this production quantitatively low, but it also presents a multiplicity of terminologies to problematize the displacement of teaching-learning activities to contexts other than the traditional classroom.

Despite the use of different terminologies, the most recurrent are technical visits, educational tourism, field trips, and field

research (Cooper, 2001; Veloso, 2003; Carvalho; Vieira & Viana, 2012). Although the analyses of the fieldwork in tourism courses in higher education in Brazil recognize the benefits of this initiative, especially with regard to the opportunity to combine theory and practice, address the theme of leisure at a superficial level, including instrumentalizing it for educational purposes. Therefore, one might ask: in what ways is fieldwork carried out by professors of undergraduate courses in tourism in Brazil and how does leisure permeate this didactic-pedagogical practice?

Meanwhile, Veloso (2003, p.65) argues that the "technical visit should not be treated as a mere tour". Brito, Ros, and Perinotto (2012), when mobilizing the category of pedagogical tourism as a privileged possibility to carry out fieldwork with didactic-pedagogical purposes, "in a playful way" (p.10), recognize the advantages of this practice with respect to student learning. Carvalho, Vieira, and Viana (2012), however, while reinforcing the importance of students planning their own trip and systematizing data collection, do not address leisure possibilities throughout the article written by themselves.

Having said this, the **purpose** of this paper is to discuss the ways in which fieldwork is present in the didactic and pedagogical practices of professors of undergraduate courses in tourism in Brazil. Moreover, **it aims** to understand how educators who make use of fieldwork understand the presence of leisure and higher education in tourism.

As a **justification** for the present investigation, we emphasize that the study has an unprecedented character, considering that, in the existing analyses, there is still no debate about the teaching practice of professors from different institutions of higher education in tourism, which articulates leisure and education.

In light of such considerations, it is appropriate to highlight the **structure** of this work, subdivided into four sections. The following item discusses the relationship between leisure and education, trying, therefore, to present how the theme of fieldwork

is present in the scientific production related to higher education in tourism in Brazil. The third section addresses the methodological procedures used throughout this investigation. Next, in section 4, the results are analyzed and discussed. Finally, by way of conclusion, the last section of this article is devoted to the final remarks.

2. Methodological remarks

This research is exploratory and descriptive in nature. Besides analyzing the curricular guidelines of higher education courses in tourism in Brazil, we sought to theoretically support this research by means of a bibliographical research. Thus, a survey was carried out on the Capes Journal Website, using the following criteria: publications without temporal delimitation and the search command "all fields". We arrived at 52 articles with the term "*fieldwork tourism course*" and, subsequently, twelve articles with the term "*technical visits tourism course*", in addition to ten articles with the following expression "*practical trips tourism course*". From the 74 papers evidenced in this stage, it is important to consider that, from the first group, 49 publications were disregarded after analyzing the abstracts, since they were not about technical visits in undergraduate courses in tourism, or they focused on different aspects of the "tourism field of work", or they were related to fieldwork in technical courses in tourism or in undergraduate courses in Geography. This leaves the publications by Schulze (2005), Nora (2011) and Mendes *et. al.* (2017).

As for the groups of works resulting from the research on "technical visits in the tourism course" and "practical trips in the tourism course", 19 works were excluded, since they are dedicated to the use of technical visits in different undergraduate courses. In addition, one study was discarded because it brought together, in the same sample, Tourism students and students from other undergraduate courses. In this way, two researches linked to the discussion of fieldwork in higher education courses in tourism were identified: the researches of Ulian (2017) and Kiyotani; Araújo and Oliveira (2022).

To investigate how professors of undergraduate courses in tourism understand fieldwork and leisure, we conducted interviews with 34 professors from 19 undergraduate courses in tourism in Brazil. These semi-structured interviews began on February 2, 2021 and lasted until April 6, 2021. They were conducted via Google Meet (except for the two respondents who submitted their answers in writing) and all signed the Informed Consent Form previously approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the university responsible for the investigation. Audio and sound recording was done by means of Movavi Screen Recorder 21 *software*.

As for the group researched, from a geographical point of view, seven interviewees come from the North Region of Brazil, four are from the South Region, three are based in the Northeast Region, five are linked to institutions in the Center-West Region, and 15 are active in the Southeast Region of the country. From a more refined spatial logic, it can be seen that five professors are connected to the state of Amazonas and two from Tocantins; from the South, three come from the state of Rio Grande do Sul, while one is from Paraná; from the Northeast region, one is linked to the state of Sergipe, another to Rio Grande do Norte and, finally, one is from the state of Piauí; from the Midwest region, one is linked to the state of Goiás, one to Mato Grosso, and three to Mato Grosso do Sul; with regard to the Southeast, three professors are from Minas Gerais, five from Rio de Janeiro, and seven from São Paulo.

Of the 19 institutions to which the teachers are committed to, two are associated with a community institution, six educators are attached to four private institutions, and 26 teachers come from 14 public institutions. When considering the modality of the courses, five respondents are associated with technology courses, while 29 are associated with a bachelor's degree in tourism. Finally, all the respondents are associated with courses whose modality is face-to-face. In order to protect the anonymity of interviewees, we chose to use codenames when mentioning

them in this paper.

As for the analysis of the statements of 34 professors of higher education courses in tourism, we have chosen to conduct the study based on tools derived from critical discourse analysis: first, we hope to discuss aspects of **lexical selection** (Fiorin, 2007), by seeking to understand the different terminologies employed in relation to the use of this teaching method. By highlighting aspects of lexical selection, we aim to identify what is the most elementary discourse strategy of the intradiscourse, in turn, the set of texts that manifest a discourse (Faria *in* Carrieri *et. al.*, 2009). Thus, in the analysis undertaken, we considered the choice of vocabulary used by the teachers, its allocation throughout the texts, and the use of certain figures of speech present in these textual records to the detriment of others.

The lexical selection, as a basic aspect present in the discourse, ends up allowing the visualization of all the other linguistic aspects, such as the identification of themes and figures, as well as the ideas defended and, consequently, the ideas combated. By recognizing that discourse is not something eminently individual, unlike speech, it is necessary to consider its social and historical dimension, which allows us to affirm that no discursive construction is neutral. This is because every discourse is also permeated by other discourses, that is, it keeps an explicit or implicit connection with other discursive manifestations, whether of opposition or affinity (Faria *in* Carrieri *et. al.*, 2009).

3. Remarks on leisure and education

First, it is appropriate to consider that leisure is related to other social phenomena, so that it is not possible to perceive it as something isolated (Gomes, 2011). Rolim (1989), Marcellino (1990), Gomes and Elizalde (2012) defend the importance of an education capable of contemplating leisure, recognizing the contributions of this sociocultural manifestation to the educational process.

One may note that leisure in the educational process is linked to several initiatives in which creativity (Rolim, 1989) and playfulness

(Gomes & Elizalde, 2012) are present. If playfulness would be based on educational experiences centered on stimulating the senses, playing, and exalting emotions (Gomes, 2014), creativity would be present mainly through practices centered on creation, invention, and the establishment of innovations in the teaching-learning process.

Articulating leisure and the initiatives carried out in the teaching-learning process implies, therefore, a certain epistemic rupture with the thesis that leisure would be a kind of "free time," which would emerge as a kind of "supposed time of freedom, of liberation from the ties, obligations, and contradictions present in the world of work" (Gomes & Elizalde, 2012, p. 122). In other words, it does not seem appropriate to conceive leisure fully disconnected from labor and education. In this sense, Gomes' (2014) proposal can point to ways to understand leisure experiences articulated to other social experiences. Hence, it makes less sense to ask whether a given experience is only in the field of leisure, in the field of work, or in the field of education. Rather, one can think not only of a socially constructed time/space for leisure, but also of experiences that are cleaved by different meanings. In this case, didactic-pedagogical actions not only understood as constituents of the educational field, but also linked to leisure.

It is assumed that leisure is, above all, a cultural manifestation. Thus, it is possible to consider that its different manifestations would be exponents of practices closely associated with an extensive symbolic network permeated with meanings, values, intentionalities, traditions, and customs. Therefore, it is relevant to recognize, as Gomes (2014) does, that leisure is a human need, and that there are different ways to satisfy this desire. Another aspect can be considered as inherent to leisure experiences: playfulness, here understood as a language focused on stimulating the senses, enjoyment, enjoyment, and intimately grounded in imagination (Gomes, 2014).

Finally, it is important to recognize another challenge in this relationship between

leisure and education: the predominance of the recreation paradigm in the teaching of undergraduate courses in tourism in the country (Anjos Júnior, 2021). Recreation, games, and pleasant activities, especially for children, would be those typologies more widely spread in the country, related to the articulations between leisure and education. Such cultural practices ended up being engendered in the teaching-learning processes, despite the role of Physical Education in this regard, to the extent that they ended up spreading practices focused on guided play as a synonym for leisure (Gomes, 2008).

Thus, it is possible to glimpse that higher education in tourism tends to continue a teaching tradition that presents ambiguities around leisure, either by ignoring it, neglecting it, or associating it with fun activities derived from game manuals and dynamics. This system corresponds to operational recreation, in which someone defines the recreational activities to be developed and the others just execute them, without any possibility of reflection about the meaning and the fundamentals of this practice.

Next, a brief summary will be made

about the presence of fieldwork and leisure in higher education courses in tourism, based on the national scientific production that discusses the theme of these field trips.

4. Brazilian academic production on fieldwork in higher education courses in tourism

It is important to point out that the Brazilian scientific production on fieldwork developed in higher education courses in tourism is scarce and incipient, as far as the articles published in journals available at the Journal Website of the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES) are concerned.

The first article on the subject identified in the database is by Schulze (2005). It was published in journal *Olhar de professor*, in the field of education. Nora (2011) is the author of the second paper (an abstract) that was published in 2011 in the Brazilian Ecotourism Journal (RBEcotur), which also published a third paper by Mendes *et al.* (2017). The fourth academic production, by Ulian (2017), was published by Revista de Graduação da USP, while a fifth paper, by Kiyotani, Araújo, and Oliveira (2022), was published in the Observatório de Inovação do Turismo academic journal.

Table 1 – Journal articles concerning fieldwork in tourism courses

<i>Paper Title</i>	<i>Keywords</i>	<i>Author(s)</i>	<i>Journal</i>
In search of Humanism: a look into technical visits in tourism courses based on the curriculum critical theory	Learning strategies, technical visit, Tourism courses, curriculum, critical theory	Schulz (2005)	Olhar de professor
O trabalho de campo para o profissional do turismo	Teaching; Ecotourism; Fieldwork	Nora (2011)	Brazilian Ecotourism Journal
The perception of the Jericoacoara National Park by UFPA tourism students	Ecotourism; Perception; Jericoacoara	Mendes, <i>et al.</i> (2017)	
O Campo como Laboratório: Relevância das Viagens Didáticas na Formação do Profissional em Lazer e Turismo – Estudo de Meio em Curitiba/PR	Curitiba; Leisure and Tourism; Didactic Trip.	Ulian (2017)	Revista De Graduação USP
Breaking Down Walls: Field trips as a teaching-learning methodology in tourism courses	Tourism. Teaching-learning process. Field trips. Educational praxis	Kiyotani; Araújo; Oliveira (2022)	Revista Acadêmica Observatório de Inovação do Turismo

Source: the authors

Table 1 allows us to visualize not only a small Brazilian academic production on the

subject of fieldwork in tourism undergraduate courses, but also that the existing material is

dispersed over a relatively long time span of 17 years.

In this academic production, it is noteworthy that lexical diversity is present in the very denomination of the fieldwork. If the works by Schulze (2005) and Mendes *et al.* opt for the syntagma "technical visit", in line with the curricular guidelines for Tourism courses (Brazil, 2006), the research by Nora (2011) and Ulian (2017) make use of the syntagma "field work", although the term "didactic trips" is present in the title. The article by Kyotani, Araújo and Oliveira, on the other hand, mentions "field visits".

Schulze (2005) advocates for the technical visit as an important teaching-learning strategy in tourism and that it is not exhausted in itself, given the need, according to the author, to value the post-visit. There is also criticism of technical visits oriented only to discuss the marketing aspects of tourism, thus disregarding an entire socioeconomic and sociocultural context marked by exclusion and inequality, as one may note in different regions in Brazil. Finally, there is the support for a cooperative logic of organization of the technical visit, in which students can be open to the construction and problematization of this practice together with the professor.

For Nora (2011), it is essential to enable technical visits: a logic that advocates that the tourism professional should experience tourist experiences similar to the activities with which he or she will work after graduating. From what we can gather from the text, the initiative aims at a broadening of the range of activities around tourism. By this logic, little room has been left in the reflection for personal experiences other than those centered on professional aspects.

Mendes *et al.* (2017) identifies fieldwork as an important tool for the democratization of tourist destinations, considering that several undergraduate students of the higher education course in tourism at the Federal University of Pará had never been on a hike, an action made possible during the visit to the National Park of Jericoacoara, in the State of

Ceará.

The author explains aspects that are usually silenced in discussions about this learning strategy: the capacity that technical visits have to foster new life experiences to the students, thus broadening the horizons not only of theoretical and methodological elements of tourism and the labor market, but of individuals themselves.

In Kiyotani, Araújo, and Oliveira's (2022) research, the concern of the authors in pointing out their understanding of fieldwork is evident. Moreover, repeatedly throughout the document, there is the defense of the inseparability between theory and practice, that is, the need to recognize that "articulating theory-field becomes key to reflections from students, fostering research and conflict resolution" (p. 6).

However, electing knowledge and sustaining the rigor of knowledge for technical production relies, in many cases, on the idea that only scientific knowledge is worthy of credibility. Any forms of knowledge that are not grounded in scientific rigor are not recognized as science and are thus marginalized by Western thought (Santos, 2010). For Santos (2010, p.102), the monoculture of knowledge would be the production mode of a very powerful non-existence, since it "consists of transformation of modern science and high culture into unique criteria of truth and aesthetic quality" and, therefore, there is a relativization of erudite and academic knowledge. Therefore, the text excerpts reveal that the binomial university and technical visit have a relationship that is sometimes marked by dispute, and sometimes by complicity.

Such an understanding invisibilizes, among other practices, the experiences permeated by leisure in fieldwork. It would obliterate opportunities for dialogue with students about their impressions around reality and themselves, reinforcing the paradigm of a Cartesian education dissociated from other sociocultural phenomena.

Ulian's work (2017) describes the experience of a fieldwork for the course in Tourism and Transportation, held in Curitiba, which

engaged 89 students from the tourism and leisure course at University of São Paulo - USP. The goal was to grasp elements of different means of transportation. This resumes Masetto's (2003) assumptions, when he defends not only the importance of teaching in universities taking place in other environments than just the classroom, but also the relevance of a greater link "between higher education and the world of work" (p.21). The recognition of the students' leisure experiences draws attention in this work, especially because they could have a complementary role in enriching the experiences rather than in competing with the work proposal. As expressed by a tourism student:

I think our didactic journey [...] helped elucidate concepts that we see within the academic world. Not only with regard to transportation, but the other aspects of tourism and leisure as well. [...] (Uilian, 2017, p. 127).

Although the author emphasizes, in her final considerations, the importance of fieldwork for the visualization of elements related to the work of tourismologists, the aforementioned article highlights students' perspectives. By giving voice to them, it makes explicit their respective readings of this practice, including by also associating it with leisure.

5. Field works and leisure: Professors' perspectives

Broadly speaking, the 34 interviews were arranged under the logic of six fundamental themes and, consequently, their associated figures. The thematic path most commonly perceived throughout the interviews generally followed the following arrangement: Education, as an initial theme, followed by the themes related to audiovisual, tourism, new technologies, and then work and leisure.

On the subject of leisure, it is noteworthy that, when asked about the possibilities of visualizing elements of leisure in higher education in tourism, 5 educators explicitly mentioned doing fieldwork. Another 3 educators pointed out that they encourage the students to go to the field, but not during class time, usually with the purpose of registering images for audiovisual productions requested by the

educator in charge of the course.

The absence of this pedagogical practice (fieldwork) was noted in 26 interviews. The silence about this practice may indicate that, institutionally, it is not encouraged and/or possible, since some educators pointed out management problems in the universities to which they are linked.

The 5 professors who make recurrent use of fieldwork in their tourism courses are referred to here, using pseudonyms, as *José*, *Scarlett*, *Cecília*, *Michael*, and *Moore*. These professors are responsible for the following courses:

Table 2 – Subjects taught by professors who carried out fieldwork

<i>Educator</i>	<i>Course(s)</i>
José	Mobility
Scarlett	Psychology Applied to Tourism; Environment and Tourism
Cecília	Philosophy applied to Tourism – Research techniques applied to Tourism I and II
Michael	Food and Beverage Planning and Management, and Psychological Aspects of Tourism
Moore	General Tourism Theory; Interdisciplinary Tourism Project; Thematic Fields

Source: the authors

José's mention of fieldwork brings with it other themes related to education: the audiovisual theme, through the figure "videos", work, seen in the figure "work groups", and leisure, seen in the activities that would be developed along the trip.

The objective of the fieldwork, according to the educator, is to allow not only the tourism students to experience the different modes of transportation, but also to exercise a set of skills related to routing, resource management, and reservation operationalization in lodging facilities. In this way they experience, in practice, some of the tasks that are likely to be performed by tourist experts.

From the point of view of lexical selection, the teacher calls the practice a "didactic trip", since the trip is made to a different city from the one where the students are bound. In addition, the teacher gives students the

opportunity to design the trip themselves, so that all students have some assignment associated with the activity, something close to the perspective adopted by Schulze (2005) highlighted above.

However, when asked if it would be possible to visualize elements of leisure in that experience, the educator attests that: "I don't know if he was in a leisure moment, because he had a task. It involves playfulness at least" (José).

It is interesting to note, in this statement, the doubt about the presence of leisure in practice. This is because it is understood that leisure is not in the activities themselves, but that it will depend on the understanding of the subjects involved in it (Gomes, 2014), that is, it would be up to the students themselves to also perceive or not the presence of leisure. However, the learner problematizes the presence of a task (work theme) as a possible obstacle to the recognition of leisure. In a way, there is a binary logic that opposes work and leisure. It seems necessary, therefore, to consider the importance of

"[...] dichotomies, fragmentations, and hierarchizations need to be urgently addressed if social transformation and the construction of a more humane and caring world are to be possible. This can be done from many fronts, but our perspective is that resignified, problematizing, critical, synergistic and transformational leisure can be one (and not the only) important tool to mobilize counter-hegemonic intercultural and educational experiences, thus contributing to a learning for social and cultural transformation (Gomes & Elizalde, 2012, p. 129).

That said, it is appropriate to notice in the educator's excerpt that the recognition of the presence of playfulness is already a feature capable of evidencing the presence of intersecting experiences. That is, even in a didactic-pedagogical moment, it is possible to consider that students experience, articulate, and re-signify reality and themselves through playfulness, the language in which leisure is based.

The hypothesis that this teacher tends to consider the possibility of intersections between the phenomena of leisure, education, and work can be seen in another excerpt of José's statement:

"[...] I think it is fair that we can have exclusive leisure time. Seeking to superimpose these things is, perhaps, [...] not a good thing. It may be that they overlap or interpenetrate [...] but I am not sure that I would do this in an objectified way, because leisure time is the time of exchange of meanings, exchange of purposes even, so in the teaching-learning process I would make use of leisure time something a little unfair [...] if I objectified this.

As noted, there is recognition of cleavages between distinct sociocultural phenomena. This does not minimize, however, the very importance of having institutionalized times for leisure, as evidenced by Isayama and Gomes (2006) and Gomes (2008).

Another educator who makes use of fieldwork is *Michael*. From the point of view of lexical selection, the lecturer opts for the syntagma "field work". The themes of education and travel materialize here in the figures of the students and of a Private Natural Heritage Reserve (RPPN) in the countryside of the State of Paraná. In this case, the goal is to experience adventure tourism, much as a result of a reflection on the psychological aspects present in tourism.

When asked about the presence of leisure elements throughout the course, the educator states that he can perceive this sociocultural phenomenon, not least because he has "[...] no doubt that it is important to work on the playful aspects, and that will result later in the pedagogical process" (*Michael*). It is noteworthy that fieldwork was the first teaching practice he mentioned when asked about the topic of leisure.

This educator also makes use of elements such as play, games, and jokes in his classes. He feels that all of this would take "some of the burden off of the obligation of that rigid content." [...]. As it is also observed,

the recognition of the power of leisure ends up being mobilized to overcome certain limits of a traditional higher education, since it is tiresome, often boring, and centered on the memorization of contents, generally transmitted from written texts (Anjos Júnior, 2021). If fieldwork has, on the one hand, the advantage of stimulating tourism students to engage in the teaching-learning process, it can, on the other hand, hide, through the use of more vivid elements, the real challenge: the limits of a higher education in tourism that, in the long run, can be discouraging.

In turn, *Moore* uses the fieldwork via holding events such as music festivals and film screenings aimed at elementary school children. It is curious to note that, in this case, there is no desire to observe elements of a hypothetical professional reality of the future tourist, but the mobilization with a view to intervening in a given reality. Therefore, there is less of a practice associated with interaction between students and aspects of the world of work in tourism, and more of a relationship between students and different forms of organization in society.

When asked if she sees elements of leisure in these practices, the educator signals positively, including by mentioning the presence of the popcorn figure. Although it is a figure associated with the theme of food, it was mentioned as capable of attesting to the joy and relaxation of the event, which, according to her, would be expressions of leisure.

The teacher also points out that one of the objectives of these practices capable of mobilizing the students' fieldwork has to do with the attempt to integrate community-university. It is possible to consider that, in this case, the educator brings aspects of university extension to the dimension of higher education in tourism, that is, she promotes the articulation between university and society through different initiatives.

Another initiative concerning the presence of the fieldwork is carried out by *Cecilia*. She conducts, in her own words, "City tours" with the students from the higher education

course in tourism at the institution where she works. In this case, the *city-tour* syntagma refers more explicitly to the theme of tourism, in this case pedagogical tourism, which, by the way, is one of the forms mobilized to structure fieldwork, as perceived in the work of Brito, Ros, and Perinotto (2012).

When asked about the reasons for adopting such a practice, the teacher said that, unlike her peers, she would not be losing teaching hours. Rather, she considers that they, the students, "gained knowledge and a knowledge that they will carry for life" (*Cecilia*). Such logic tends to go against the results obtained in the research of Anjos (2021), when the researcher found that, among the teachers of higher education courses in tourism in Brazil, there is an emphasis on dealing with contents related to teaching plans, minimizing other possibilities for developing competencies, as advocated by the curricular guidelines in the area:

Art. 4 The undergraduate course in Tourism must enable professional training that reveals, at least, the following competencies and abilities:

[...] X – mastery of techniques related to the selection and evaluation of geographic, historical, artistic, sports, recreational, and entertainment, folkloric, handicraft, gastronomic, religious, political, and other cultural traits, as diverse forms of manifestation of the human community;

[...] XII – interpersonal, intercultural communication and correct and precise expression about specific technical aspects and the interpretation of the reality of organizations and the cultural traits of each community or social segment (Brazil, 2006, p. 2-3)

Thus, something relevant in *Cecilia's* practice is the commitment to enabling the flowering of stimulating feelings, of dreams, of imaginative aspects in the academic environment. And the fieldwork would be one of those in charge of favoring that this subjective dimension of the student could be valued. It might be something close to the following

logic:

[...] Leisure can give identity (individual and collective) and autonomy to those who live it. Thus, education based on transformational learning linked to leisure may deliver the possibility of experiencing educational processes as something of one's own and not as something external, compulsory and imposed by others (Gomes & Elizalde, 2012, p. 155).

The educator corroborates the aforementioned perspective, when education is considerably permeated by leisure elements. This is because afterwards, she states, when asked about the possibility of viewing leisure in tourism higher education, the following:

Building knowledge is not something that we need to do in a closed and serious way, is it? I think that we have ways to produce good content, to produce knowledge and to do this in a light way, in the sense that people understand what we are talking about and what we are proposing to do, [...] In this context, producing these sensibilities is an important thing, because [...] leisure is not just standing there with your head up in the air [...] it has the ability to acquire knowledge that you may not even be aware that you are acquiring" (Cecília).

As it can be seen, the *city-tour* figure, derived from the theme of tourism, is heavily impregnated by the theme of leisure and education. And the educator's position is in line with the logic defended by Masetto (2003) when he reinforces the thesis that teaching does not need to be confined only to the classroom.

Finally, *Scarlet* mobilizes fieldwork in her teaching practice through the syntagma "technical visit". In this case, it can be seen, through the objectives of the initiative, that the purpose was, in fact, to bring future tourism graduates closer to the reality of the world of work in the area. The students would have to evaluate whether members of a community located in an Environmental Preservation Area were fit to receive tourists. In this case, not only would students play the role of researchers in measuring the experience of

the visit, but they would also play the role of visitors, being able to reflect on the subjects involved in the tourism field. This educator also considers the presence of leisure in her tourism teaching practices.

Final remarks

Fieldwork in higher education courses in tourism is explicit in the curricular guidelines of these degrees. Even though it is called technical visits, a type of fieldwork closely identified with theoretical and practical content and that sometimes minimizes the observation of elements other than those legitimized in the teaching plans, there is little scientific production on the subject. It was also notable the presence of different terminologies to refer to the fieldwork, which may give rise to a fruitful field of investigation, as we try to better understand the differences between the different expressions used.

In the bibliographical research, we noticed the prevalence of a higher education model that prioritizes academic knowledge and the centrality of content in the teaching-learning process, although part of the research points out the benefits of fieldwork for the development of skills and personal enrichment. In addition, predominance of the correlation between field work and improvement in the professional conduct of future graduates was noteworthy, which makes it difficult for other expertise, possibilities, and knowledge coming from these experiences to be valued.

Of the five articles selected and analyzed, one of them does not deal with leisure: "O trabalho de campo para o profissional do turismo". The article "Breaking Down Walls: Field trips as a teaching-learning methodology in tourism courses" holds a negative view of this social phenomenon, by understanding it as a risk to the loss of seriousness and the students' engagement when in the field, behavior that is desired for a good use of this teaching strategy. These two ways of thinking about leisure (silencing and caveat) would be aligned with a hegemonic logic that subordinates social phenomena and knowledge other than those socially legitimated, such as work,

education, and science.

Two other texts associate leisure with tourism only, not explicitly visualizing leisure elements throughout fieldwork: "In search of Humanism: a look into technical visits in tourism courses based on the curriculum critical theory" and the text "The perception of the Jericoacoara National Park by UFPA tourism students". However, in this last paper, the recognition regarding the presence of student testimonies attesting to the satisfaction of making trails for the first time would be a clue to the presence of playfulness, although leisure is not addressed throughout the article.

The work "O Campo como Laboratório: Relevância das Viagens Didáticas na Formação do Profissional em Lazer e Turismo – Estudo de Meio em Curitiba/PR" deals with leisure not only as a possible field of action for students, but also as a component present in fieldwork, even if this is done in an implicit way. Such comprehension favors the understanding that leisure is not something capable of competing with higher education in tourism, but a phenomenon that can contribute to a transforming, critical, dialogical education, committed to valuing the knowledge, the readings, and the experiences of the students, even transcending scientific knowledge.

As for the analysis of the presence of fieldwork in the teaching practice of the interviewed professors, there are some observations. In general, they recognize the presence of leisure in the fieldwork, although they name this experience in different ways. It is noteworthy that, although all the fieldwork presented very specific objectives, it was not always limited to the contents emanating from the teaching plans. *Cecilia* and *Moore* advocate for a more libertarian education, more stimulating and capable of developing interpersonal and intrapersonal relationship

skills. Even because of this, there is more openness in recognizing other reactions from the students, not necessarily those coming from evaluative activities.

On the other hand, *José, Michael, and Scarlet*, despite the emphasis on the correlations with the contents taught, although they do not explain in detail the ways in which leisure manifests itself in this teaching practice, recognize, although in different ways, the presence of leisure in these actions.

Still with regard to the interviews, it is worth noting that all five educators who use fieldwork recognize the presence of leisure in this teaching practice.

When comparing the surveys conducted in higher education courses in tourism in Brazil about fieldwork and the use of this teaching practice among the interviewees, some points are noticeable: firstly, there is a diffusion of terminology, with emphasis on technical visits, educational trips, and terms referring to tourism, such as city-tour.

A second point worth noting is the certain ambiguity regarding the presence of leisure. When not silenced, its presence, when legitimized, is not made very explicit by the teachers, who are more concerned, it seems, with the search for fulfilling the tasks programmed for the subjects.

A third aspect that can be investigated in the future is the observation, in the pedagogical projects of higher tourism courses in Brazil, of the terms by which fieldwork is understood, as well as the presence of leisure in these documents. This is justified, among other things, by the absence of mentions of this teaching practice among the 26 professors of tourism courses who were interviewed. This silence may be based on the absence of this practice in the curricula of undergraduate courses in the country.

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